

THE ROLE OF LECTURER IN IMPROVING COLLEGE QUALITY LEARNING

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Abstract

Lecturer as one of an essential component in universities where their existence very important associated with Roles, Assignments, Responsibilities to achieve National Education to transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology and education arts, research and community service as the main tasks. Therefore, the lecturers are required to have a pedagogical, personality, social and professional competencies that aims to describe the role in relation to learning quality in college. This exposure is expected to broaden the knowledge of lecturers and universities policy makers to improve learning process quality in order to produce quality of graduates as well. The methodology research used was literature. It means that, researchers used literature, either in the form of books, records, and reports of previous research results that achieved in this study, there were four productivity through learning quality improvements (1). Goal-Congruent Lecturers and College,(2). Learning system,(3). Lecturers Paradigm and (4). College objectives quality therefore lecturers always trying to improve their knowledge, lecturers can follow higher education, should keep in touch to the latest technology, always aware of their responsibility to help students to be the best, and always trying to prepare the best learning lessons. Lecturer as a determinant factor of learning quality has responsibility as the organizer. To teach well, lecturer needs to perform a self-evaluation, integrated control and as educators and teachers especially in higher education Timor Leste is currently in the development. Process of the lecturers need for a greater commitment of collage management as well as support from the government in order to increase resources for sustainable human can answer the needs of quality and achievement in order to target the scope of competition and the implementation can meet the requirements.

Keywords: Lecturer, Learning Quality and College.

INTRODUCTION

Lecturer is one of the essential components in collage. Their existence is very important associated with roles, tasks, responsibilities to achieve the objectives the National Education's goal. To reach the goal of national education Profesional Lecturer is needed, to expressed as professional educators and scientists with the main task to transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology, and the arts of education, research, and public service. So, it needs an evaluation for lecturers in order to carry out their duties and responsibilities in line with what is required in law. It is expected to increase the quality of the lecturers so that the quality of students and the collage will also increases.

The existance of lecturers with professional ability and close relationship to the students and colleagues in universities is very important. Lecturers are determine the development of institution, because they can affect intellectual environment and social life of the campus. Besides that, the role of lecturers were important in coloring curriculum, academic regulatory control, as well as creating a climate learning of student. So it is not excessive if it is saying that the lecturer is the person who most know the real process of education in campus, in this case the lecturers have a position as a designer, implementers and evaluators of education and teaching process.

Higher education is the most valuable national asset in any country. Higher education now is not treated as a luxury product; but as national development asset, social and economic (Peril and Janji,2000). In higher education, the quality concept today is more complex and opposed to an industry where the final product is clear. *Harvey and Green* agree that the fundamental difference between higher education and other service providers through the process of transformation of higher education are often involved cognitive transcendence on the student and not only provide a service for them. However, rapid changes in higher education today has significantly narrowed the gap where university viewed as a quality organization. The concerns about quality of higher education is always exist and seen in many ways. Due to an increasingly diverse student profile, it is imperative that ' the stakeholders's views need a relatively high to proof because it contained four productivity through improved quality of learning: (1). Goal-Congruent Lecturers and College,(2). Learning system,(3). Lecturers Paradigm and (4). College objectives quality. Therefore lecturers always trying to improve their knowledge, they can follow higher education, should keep in touch to the latest technology, always aware of their responsibility to help students to be the best, and always trying to prepare the best learning lessons.

Learning Quality

According to Juran in Makawimbang (2011:42), quality is as "a place for life" and insisted that the mission of university basic quality is "to develop programs and services that meet the needs of users such as students and public." Meanwhile, according to ISO 2000 in Suhana (2014:77), the quality is characteristics total of a products (goods and services) that support the ability to satisfy the requirement that is specified or defined. Based on above description indicates that the quality is an opportunity to put in a competitive position. It means that it accordance to the expectations of user satisfaction. Quality of teaching is determined by three variables, namely higher education culture, teaching learning, and reality of college. College culture is the values, customs, rituals, slogans, and any behaviors that have long formed in college and passed on from generation to the next generation, either conscious or unconsciously. This culture is believed to affect the behavior of all components of higher education, namely lecturers, heads of colleges, administrative staff, students, and parents of students. The conducive culture improvement quality will encourage citizens behavior in improving quality of higher education, otherwise not conducive culture will impede efforts in improving the quality of higher education.

In connection to the components that make up the education system, *Syaodih more detailed (2012:3) argues that input components are classified into three, namely:(1) Raw input, such as intellect, physical health, social-affective and peer group students.(2) Instrumental input, covering education policy, programs (curriculum), personnel (university leaders, teachers, staff), facilities, media, and costs. (3) Environmental inputs, including the college environment, family environment, community, and social institutions, the work unit.* The components process according to Syaodih, et al (2012:6) includes teaching, training, coaching, evaluating, extracurricular, and management. Furthermore, the output includes knowledge, personality and performance. Based on above opinion, it is known that the learning process is education system component that can determine the success of learning and education quality. Therefore, to obtain a good education quality of education , quality learning process is required.

The Role of Lecturer in Improving Quality of College Learning

In college, a lecturer holds an important role for the progress of institution. It has long been recognized by the lecturer himself. This awareness is demonstrated by personal efforts to make themselves have competence and expertise in accordance with the interests and occupied areas because lecturers have academic atmosphere that can determine quality teaching at the college include:

Goal-Congruent Lecturers and College

Based on this idea, a lecturer has a high academic ego, one manifestation of this attitude is the "pulpit academic freedom". Why, manage a lecturer becomes very difficult? That is the answer, because the lecturer has an academic high-ego. The actualization of a lecturer, to be himself with the expertise, to be high. Expertise sometimes makes boxes that are difficult to put together, though ruled by the same college. There is not any going goal- congruent, no alignment of interest between the vision, mission and personal goals with the vision, mission and objectives of the institution. Starting from here, college quality problems arise. Understanding the vision, mission and goals of the institution are derived in institutional quality objectives that should be understood to be a reference and directions of a lecturer in devote their expertise to achieve college quality objective.

Learning System

The model development of current learning has rapidly advanced. From the model focuses on the teacher center-change to student center. Many universities have made the learning process from teacher center to student center, though not all universities are significantly make student center learning process. Bottles may be different, but the content remains the same. Here is what happened. Why this is so, it turns to paradigm of lecturers that can not be changed. It is often found in teaching practices in everyday life, lecturers still dominates in learning process and learning evaluation is determined by the results of the final exam. Student center learning system requires paradigm change perpetrators of both lecturer and student learning. Lecturer acts as facilitator and motivator, while students act as active perpetrators and independent learners. The existance of lecturer is not only the source of learning materials but as a source of learning materials, and the students as the user of learning materials.

Lecturer Paradigm

The role of lecturer in the student center learning system, much more as service providers of learning or learning provider. Because of the role of provider, then a lecturer should change the paradigm. Providers will be left behind by its customers if it is not able to meet the satisfaction and needs of customers. The services that are able to meet the satisfaction and customer requirements are called quality services. So, in order the quality service maintained its consistency, then all processes must be standardized in a system.

The quality of educational services and learning in college lies at the level of absorption of graduates or alumni in the community. If the lecturer able to provide a source of learning and keep the process of delivering a basis consistently, so as to meet the satisfaction and needs of their students as promised in academic guide book, it is considered the lecturers qualified and professionals.

Therefore, a lecturer must have focus customer paradigm, process management systems and corporate institution result.

Corporate management result institution, means that a lecturer does not just focus on the results obtained to individually but should think towards the achievements of the institution (corporate). The Achievement of a high lecturer individually does not mean anything if it is not in line with the goals, mission and vision of the institution. Similarly, in terms of learning. A lecturer should be able to manage the courses so that the result oriented responsibility to the achievement of quality objectives and programs of study, faculty quality objectives and ultimately the quality objectives of the university.

Learning Quality Goals

The steps that need to be able to realize this, begin with the design of the curriculum, the learning process up to standards of assessment. Preparation of design curriculum directed to meet the satisfaction and user needs. Learning implementation is divided into several stages of learning activities. At every stage of the learning activities are set indicators achievements, and level indicators have become a basic component of assessment. Based on this assessment component, it can be determined and assigned students' final grades. To measure the success rate of a lecturer in learning process, it is necessary to target the quality of learning of the subjects that he has.

If any lecturer prepare the learning quality goals in each semester, then overall process of the course can be known. Based on learning quality goals, the program of study are able to assess the success rate of the learning process of all courses that were organized. When all lecturers have done so, the learning quality goals can be increased again for the course. Furthermore, to the faculty level and ultimately to the university level. Therein lies the role of lecturer in improving the achievement of learning quality goals of university or college. In other words, the role lecturer in improving the achievement of learning quality goals in university initiated by compiling courses that he/she had. Learning quality goals of this study need to be set in guidelines for students, it is intended that students aware and able to control lecturers in teaching.

The Role of Lecturer in Development Institutions

The Development of college institutions that include the structure and the process can not be separated from the position and role of lecturers in these institutions. colleges that have a core mission to develop and apply knowledge through practice Tridharma put the lecturer as the main human resources based on the fact that the faculty have intellectual ability, professional, personal and social. Therefore, any decision-making over the mission of college must fully involve lecturers.

Lecturers as an important element in college, therefore lecturer's role as a teacher in the learning process also have some role which is closely related to efforts to improve the the development quality of learning in institutions including:

- a) The role of lecturer as a researcher/disseminators of information, according to Boyer (1987) stated that the ability of lecturers consists of two directions; teaching is important, but research and publications is much more important, because the reputation of a lecturer not only at teaching but also through research and write lecturers can also enhance its reputation through; presentation of papers in seminars, writing articles, journal writing national/international and preparation of compiling the book.

- b) The role of lecturer as an academic community is required the abilities of lecturer to think logically and critically, and able to communicate the results of research that led to a more responsive to the developments in technology, social sciences and culture. So that a lecturer as an academic community should also support the implementation of the community service because without the participation of lecturer is practically unable to fulfill the task of community service.
- c) The role of the lecturer as citizens can not be separated from the developments in society because the involvement in community service activities and campus residents is also an "answering" from the community itself. This was followed by *IN LOCO PARENTIS* principle which states that the lecturer acting as caregivers to "replace the function of the elderly" who have the obligation to guide students both on campus and individually (Kerr,1982).

Determinant Factors of Lecturer's Role in Enhancing Quality of College Learning

Determinant quality of the components and college graduates, made up of many components, including quality of academic program, human resources, facilities, and academic atmosphere. Various components of the quality needs to be improved in order to meet national education standards. Based on preliminary observations supported by the results of interviews with the leaders of several PTS in Timor Leste (April 2015), guaranteeing quality of teaching by lecturers at the university has yet to become major priority. That is, the quality of education, research, and community service as well as regular. In terms of quality achievement the third dharma universities, can be explained as follows. For teaching quality, can be viewed from lecturers class attendance and the data can be said have not too bad quality because lecturer average attendance in the class obtained figures by 70 % from setting standard. In fact, for universities which has internal quality assurance agency.

Lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task to transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology and the arts through education, research, and community service. The existence of lecturers as professionals works to improve the dignity and role of lecturers teaching agent, developer of science, technology, and art, as well as community service serves to improve the quality of national education. Lecturer at the college has a strategic role in terms of academic and student coaching side. Lecturers are professionals who establish the best thing for the students based on professional judgment. Many acknowledgment stating that education quality development can be pursued through lecturers quality development. This is evident from the findings of previous studies that the prevailing education "the man behind the system" (Miller, 1980: 76), man is a key factor that determines the power of education. In fact, education as services industry is the "front line providers and Determine the quality of service delivery system", the lecturer is a person who is on the forefront in determining the quality of service (Sallis,2002:35). The College success of innovative, quality, and responsive to global developments and local challenges, lies in the development effort.

According to Ritzer and Goodman (2003:117), described as the role of social interactions that play according to what is established by culture. In keeping with role theory, the role of expectations is an understanding that leads a person to behave in everyday life. According to this theory, a person who work as lecturers are expected to behave in accordance with the duties and obligations imposed as a lecturer.

Therefore, a teacher can play a role if it is capable and has undertaken the task of education, research, and community service. The task means identical with performance, which is a set of behaviors that are relevant to the purpose of the organization or organizational unit where people work (Sudarmanto,2009:9).

Theoretically, many factors can affect the role of the lecturer. Sopiah (2008:23) states that the factors that influence individual behavior is the effort, abilities and the environmental situation. According to Muchlas (2008:84), adult personality and behavior are influenced by heredity and environment with a 'variable between' situational conditions. According to Wirawan (2009:7), the performance is the result of the synergy of a number of factors, namely: the organization's internal environmental factors, external environmental factors and internal factors of employees. Mathis & Jackson (2006:113) says that the factors that affect the individual work includes individual abilities (talents, interests, personality, etc.), the level of work done (motivation, ethics, attendance, etc.), and support organizations (cultural, equipment and technology).

According to Castteter (1996: 271), the factors that can affect a person's role is derived from the internal lecturers themselves, within the organization, and the external environment. Sources from within his form among others: the weakness of the intellectual, physiological weakness, demotivation, personality factors, obsolescence or aging, preparation position, and value orientation. The sources from within the organization include: organizational system, organizational roles, behaviors that associated with monitoring, organizational climate, and organizational culture. Sources from the external environment, such as: family, economic, political, legal, social values, the labor market, changes in technology, and associations.

The role of lecturers in quality assurance in college in research is defined as the expected behavior of a lecturer, in terms of the implementation of the tasks of teaching, research, and community service. Since the behavior or performance of the lecturer is influenced by many factors, the assessment of the role of lecturer in quality assurance is necessary to study the factors that influence it, such as leadership, organizational culture, competence and accomplishment motivation.

Lecturer is one component of the university's quality determinants. Lecturer has a role in guaranteeing the quality of teaching, research, and the community services. Behavior or faculty performance is influenced by various factors, such as leadership, organizational culture, competence and accomplishment motivation.

Lecturer Responsibility in Learning

The duties and responsibilities of a lecturer, the requirements to become a qualified lecturer, to evaluate the quality of lecturers, the role of which can be done by its officers, employees and lecturers themselves in the framework of continuous improvement of quality, is a matter that absolutely need to be done by a high institution. All of these things need to be understood and implemented by the academic community to achieve vision and mission of the college. With continuous improvement of this quality of lecturers, it is hoped the college will be able to win competition both in the present and in the next age of global market. Therefore in this discussion will be discussed the role of lecturer in the learning process activities that should be done, how the lecturers should develop themselves to be qualified, should lecturers conduct self-evaluation in a sustainable manner, and so on.

a. Lecturer as Organizer

Teaching can be defined as a learning organization, so the problem of how to teach well that connect with learning organizing on how to get the desired results. Teaching can be seen as the establishment of a situation as expected or desired in which learning process can take place effectively. This situation is rather difficult and requires several components that learning process can take place effectively and produce quality results. It is necessary for important components include: The presence of students; the existence of facilities, time and place for meetings, books for the learning process; regular procedures and understandable for presentation, discussion and evaluation; The evaluation so that lecturer and students can determine the course of learning process; and the existence of organizers that were able to bring all of the above into a single unit, namely the lecturers.

Basically, a lecturer is an organizer in which the task of organizers is to create groups or individuals who are in it can function effectively to achieve the same goal together. This is the precise role of a lecturer and he/she is expected to prevail as the organizer who has the characteristics among others that have good organizational functions not as an autocrat. He/she did not make all the decisions or orders to any person what to do with the details and how and when to do it. Poor organizer unlike other members of group without the rights, privileges and special powers. Groups still need positive leadership in order to function effectively, it can clarify the objectives and achieve the desired results.

Good organizer helps the group and individuals in it to discover, formulate and clarify their goals. He/she is not only explained to the students that they have to learn, do this and that. He/she will try to delegate responsibility and distribute as widely as possible. He/she will educate groups and individuals to organize themselves so that can be done it. Lecturers as organizationally should be able to generate and assess initiatives but these initiatives are not washed away and deviate from the track. Initiatives must be within the framework goals of the class. Lecturers are able to build upon the strengths not the suppression of weakness. He/she must always has the assumption that everyone is able to achieve a goal that may result slightly different to the expected and desired by the organizers. In addition, lecturers are able to generate self-criticism and evaluation in the group and can explain the part where section he/she had worked and where he/she failed. And no less important that the lecturer as a good organizer should exercise to control so that common goals can be achieved.

The points at the top are characteristics operation of a good organizer. A lecturer is an organizer who works different from a factory manager, director of the company or the administrator colleges/universities, but basically a college lecturer as organizer other fields, will always be associated with a person, the student. Duties and responsibilities of the lecturer is to create a situation where students can work and achieve the best results.

b. How do Lecturers Can Teach Well

Being a qualified lecturer needs to understand the way of good teaching. Richard Leblanc, a professor from York University, quoted in Materials semiloka Assessment in UBINUS Jakarta (2001), suggests that there are 10 main conditions for good teaching: First, a good teaching does not only motivate students to learn, but to teach them to learn and do things in a relevant way, meaningful and memorable. Good teaching is concerned with maintaining expertise, if we have a penchant in this

maintenance, it is necessary to convey this indulgence to everyone, especially students. Second, a good teaching concerned with the substance and treatment of the student as knowledge customer. Good teaching is concerned with doing the best and always at the top in their field, read the sources either inside or outside his/her field of expertise and become a leader as long as possible. Third, good teaching is concerned with the process of listening, asking, being responsive, and remembering that each students and classes have differences. Fourth, good teaching is not always concerned with the fixed and rigid agenda, but should be flexible and not rigid and also can experiment.

Fifth, good teaching is also concerned with the style. Good and effective teaching not always stick with both hands on the table or eyes is always attached to a transparent and speak boring. The good lecturer should be able to process classroom and students. Lecturers should realize that he is a conductor with the class and students as orchestra and will play different instruments with different skill levels. Sixth, good teaching also concerned with humor. Humor can break the ice in the classroom and students can learn in a more relaxed atmosphere. Seventh, good teaching is concerned with maintaining and developing the mind and talent, devoting time (often invisible) to each student, assessing, designing and preparing materials.

Eighth, good teaching need to be supported by strong leadership and has a real vision and support the institution. Ninth, good teaching is concerned with the provision of advice to the senior and junior members or teamwork. Effective teaching needs to be rewarded, poor teaching should be improved through training and development programs. And Tenth, good teaching related to obtaining pleasure. Good teachers will practice skills that are not solely for the sake of money or because of necessity but they really enjoy and want to do.

c. Lecturers Need To Do Self-Evaluation

The rapid developments in science and technology demanding every lecturer to keep up the pace of development, so that what is taught in the classroom is not out of date. So every lecturer is required to always learn continuously either inside or outside his/her field of expertise. In this world there is no perfect lecturer, but there is always room for someone to do improvements. A lecturer must always ask himself/herself, whether it has been fulfilling its responsibilities as a lecturer and perform a good way of teaching in accordance with the requirements put forward by Prof. Leblanc ?. If the question has been raised, the next question is how to identify which aspects of good teaching methods and which aspects of teaching that needs to be changed?. The answer is the evaluation but then the next question arises who should do this?. Evaluation is an inherent part of good teaching in a person, because of that, the lecturers must take responsibility to conduct the evaluation. By doing a self-evaluation, a lecturer know how good their teaching method and what parts need to be improved.

Several reasons can be put forward regarding to the importance of evaluation for a lecturer who teaches at the college including the following: First, every lecturer who has taught well or not well enough, all have a chance to become better with time. Some lecturer were able to get better in a short time, but others get better in time mediocrity. While some lecturers became worse than their previous condition. Why did it happen? That differences occur due to the use of the information obtained from the evaluation on how to teach properly and make efforts to correct the deficiency.

Second, the evaluation by lecturer could be used for the documentation to the agency about the quality of lecturers in it. Institutions can use this document to communicate with lecturer and help him/her to constantly improve its ability in various ways.

Third, evaluation related to human needs to get psychological satisfaction. If a lecturer doing work well, then he/she will has a pleasant experience. Evaluation is a way to determine whether the work going well, but it does not mean improvement toward much better is not necessary.

Fourth, do extracting information from various sources. There are at least five sources of information that can be used to evaluate teaching method. All work done for the evaluation will use one or more sources of such information.

- 1) *Self-monitoring*, the evaluation can be acquired directly as a lecturer teach. The activity of lecturer in the classroom is to do a presentation and lead a discussion but at the same time a lecturer can know the answers of the question: How do classes take place? Do lecturers together with students or lose them? Whether the class fun or boring? Usually the answer to this question does not require a long time and can be seen at the first time teach in front of the class.
- 2) Lecturers can take advantage the use of tape recorders and video cameras. Modern technology has provided tools that are relatively accessible price that are a tape and video. Lecturers can use this tool to record events in the class and roll it back to evaluate what thing needs to be fixed.
- 3) Information from students. Students have a unique position to assist lecturer in evaluation process. If the lecturer wants to know whether a student can receive and understand the lesson well or whether the lessons were boring/interesting, then no one can answer this question correctly unless the students themselves. Based on the source of information that can be used from the students are the best source to get information about the teaching and learning process.
- 4) The test results that were obtained student. Lecturers always give the test to students both in the classroom or outside in the form of a task. Usually the purpose of the test is intended to determine the quality of the students, but at the same time the results of this test can be used to determine the quality of the lecturer. From the results of this test can be known whether the students understand the material given in class or not.
- 5) observer outside. Beside from the two parties involved in the learning process, students and lecturers, additional information can be obtained also from an independent third party and have special qualifications for example a professor or senior lecturer who participate in the classroom to observe teaching and learning process and give assessment of what they saw in terms of content. An instructional consultant can also be used to assess in terms of pedagogy and give advice on presentation techniques, procedures of discussion and ideas about active learning.

d. Integrated Quality Control

According to Feigenbaum cited by Ishikawa Kaoru (1995), the integrated quality control can be defined as "an effective system to integrate quality development, quality maintenance and efforts to improve the quality of different groups within an organization to allow production and services are at the level most economical, enabling full customer satisfaction. The most important of integrated quality control

concept is that quality control is the responsibility of all, the leader, lecturer, staff, employee and all parts. Integrated quality control is a group activity and can not be done individually. So in the context of the continuous quality improvement of lecturers in universities, it is not only responsibility of the university leaders alone but all parties involved.

To sustainably improve the quality of lecturers in universities, some basic things that can be done by lecturers to realize this desire can be described as follows: 1) lecturers should always try to improve their knowledge by reading books, browsing on the internet, writing the journal, conduct research, and attend the seminar. 2) Lecturers need to increase their knowledge by following a higher education. 3) Lecturers must follow the development of information technology so that they can use Internet to improve their knowledge and is expected to make a simple homepage to put teaching materials that can be accessed by all students. 4) Lecturers must always realize his/her responsibility to help students to be the best by mastering the content and methods and preparing learning materials as well as possible. 5) Lecturers need to have a functional level because it will constantly improve their knowledge by conducting research and writing journals.

e. Lecturer as Educators and Teachers

Lecturers must possess qualifications required for the transmission of knowledge to students. Competent lecturers will facilitate delivery quality science and technology so that what is presented to students can be accepted and developed in accordance with the students' ability to study their chosen field of science. Associated with this qualification, a lecturer always has got the minimal functional equivalence from the National Education Ministry, with the rank of Expert Assistant. The higher functional position shows the level qualification of lecturers, either from the aspect of achievement or prestige. Besides that, lecturers should also have high discipline, also sense of responsibility for education that they provide for students. How is it possible to improve the quality of education if lecturers give lessons only 3-4 meetings each semester. So lecturer must have a great responsibility towards their students that he/she not only give a lesson carelessly. Without no efforts to improve the quality, Curriculum changes fundamentally in teaching and learning methods will be unbalanced and less effective. The improving quality of lecturers should be started from the recruitment system, upgrading lecturers, system capabilities and performance assessment, as well as the system of career advancement. Of course, improving the quality of lecturers should be accompanied by an increase of their welfare.

The capabilities of lecturer include the ability in science that will be taught and techniques in teaching. This means to increase ability of the lecturer needs to be done from two aspects: the improvement of knowledge in the field, and the ability or skill in teaching; using learning methods appropriately. Besides, it also can be seen from the classification of education (S2/S3) and the academic hierarchy. Lecturer quality management can be done by improving education to a higher stratum in PTN as well as best PTS domestic or abroad gradually. The fundamental problem commonly faced by lecturer in continuing education to S2 or S3 is on the costs of education and the relevance disciplines of knowledge. Education management is always more concerned with improving the quality of lecturers, by providing sufficient financial support in the budget revenue and University expenditure.

Besides, it also can be done by improving activities of the seminar (local, regional and national), symposium, discussion, courses and workshops, both either at the faculty and university, as well as at leading universities in the country. Improving cooperation activities with agencies, business and industry in relation to the relevance program and proportionality as an addition to insights, ways of thinking and skills for lecturers. With the synergistic linkages between government, universities and the business/industry; then the discrepancy quality of college graduates is a shared responsibility; equally to bear. The government provides guidance functions and settings, business/industry that absorb college graduates and prepares graduates with quality standards in order to fill the world of IT.

Closing

The existence of lecturer is the determining factors in achieving the goals quality of higher education, the role and the efforts undertaken by a lecturer is an indicator in achieving learning goals because in addition to his teaching duties, the lecturer has been named as the scientific environmentally sensitive academic and community. On the other hand, to improve the quality of university teaching, a lecturer also required to prioritize competence in the field of research and dedication to the community as a form of perfection towards academic achievement levels, because this will further help the reputation of lecturer at the campus and the community, to support reputation. A qualified lecturers should also be supported by scientific activities in teaching, for example; in activities of scientific national seminars/ international, in-depth research, write books to answer the needs of the development of science, technology and social societies, journals or scientific articles are considered qualified to support learning efforts. But on the other side, lecturers also have obligations which must not be abandoned as an academic responsibility; organizing learning activities, running a quality assurance system of higher education, harmonize curriculum content that appropriate and correct to the students, have full responsibility for learning process so that it can work effectively and efficiently, involve themselves in the development of the institution and evaluate all forms of learning activities in order to achieve the learning objectives.

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